

EARTH SCIENCES

SPATIO-TEMPORAL CHANGES IN STRESS AND DEFORMATION OF THE EARTH'S CRUST IN CENTRAL ARMENIA

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Abstract

This research presents the findings of hydrogeodynamic monitoring aimed at understanding the processes of the earth's crust preceding seismic events and geodynamic movements of earth's crust in Armenia. Hydrogeodynamic monitoring of crustal processes includes the study of seismic regime and water level data in hydrogeodynamic boreholes. Hydrogeodynamic precursors and precursor effects of the earthquakes that occurred were determined by changes in water dynamics in wells using the HGP (hydrogeodynamic precursors) method. The magnitude of the estimated deformation that occurred around each borehole before the earthquakes was calculated. Based on the parameters of earthquakes and the dynamics of groundwater, a map of the hydrogeodeformation field of the earth's crust in the territory of Armenia was developed. The developed map reflects the deformation of the earth's crust in stressed areas of the region. Thus, geodynamic activity of tectonic blocks of the earth's crust has been stated in the north and south-west of the territory, reflecting strong deformation according to the numerical values of the estimated deformation of the earth's crust.

Monitoring observations of water levels in hydrogeodynamic boreholes located in the listed tectonic blocks also indicate deformation of the water-bearing rocks in the boreholes. Compressive deformation of the rock is reflected in the dynamics of the water level in the form of a rise, and tensile deformation of the rock results in level decrease.

The results obtained are consistent with the fact that the stress-strain state of the study area, leading to tectonic movements of the earth's crust, is associated with the groundwater regime.

Keywords: monitoring, hydrogeodynamic, seismology, profiles, boreholes, deformation, earthquake.

Introduction

The development of this direction in contemporary science is linked to the need to study the nature of earthquakes from the point of view of geodynamic processes occurring in the earth's crust. The development of new methods for studying these processes facilitates the study of the stress-strain state of the region's crust in time and space. One of these methods - the method of hydrogeodynamic monitoring has been used in the article. Hydrogeodynamic monitoring of the earth's crust was carried out aiming to study modern tectonic movements and tracking the geodynamic processes of the earth's crust in the territory of Armenia. The method helps to identify medium-term precursors based on anomalous phenomena that precede earthquakes, the deformation of the earth's crust changes, the groundwater level decrease or increase.

The results of monitoring observations were compared with the seismic regime of the region. Seismicity is one of the sensitive indicators of the intensity of modern tectonic movements, therefore data characterizing the seismicity of the studied area are used to study the contemporary movements of the earth's crust.

The territory of Armenia is characterized by a zonal structure determined by four deep faults delimiting it: Lalvar-Mrav, Bazum-Sevan, Hankavan-Syunik

and Yerevan fault zones Geology of the USSR [2]. The fault tectonics of the territory of Armenia is characterized by many deep faults of pan-Caucasian and anti-Caucasian territories. The territory of Armenia hydrogeologically is a highly elevated drainage area and belongs to a zone of intense water exchange with the direction of surface water flow from the folded structure towards the Kur and Middle Araks depressions [5].

Monitoring Network

Observations for the monitoring purposes were carried out based on changes in water levels in hydrogeodynamic boreholes. For the placement of boreholes, areas and aquifers with a low level of uncontrolled interference were selected on the territory of Armenia in order to determine the characteristics of the regime of these horizons and their reaction to the preparation of earthquakes. The network of observation boreholes included points located both in zones of tectonic disturbances and in undisturbed areas located in seismically active areas of the Armenian region [6]. There are fifteen hydrogeodynamic boreholes on the territory of Armenia, which are distributed over three large blocks of the earth's crust, the geodynamics of which determine the seismicity of the territory. A group of informative boreholes were selected from the active boreholes according to the estimated informativeness coefficients

($K \geq 0.5$) (Fig. 1). The information content coefficient for each observation borehole of the network was determined according to the formula: $K = H / \Sigma P$ where H is the observed number of precursors, ΣP is the calculated number of precursors [10]. The assessment of the

information content of the boreholes was determined by recording tidal variations, by changing the water level and the sensitivity of the borehole locations (proximity to a deep fault) [8].

Fig.1 Map of active faults on the territory of Armenia with a network of observation points.
1-hydrogeodynamic boreholes - numerator - borehole number, denominator information coefficient,
2- active faults (authors: Karakhanyan A.S.,).

The method of hydrogeodynamic (HGD) precursors was applied for processing the results [8]. The study in the region using this method was carried out to study the regime of groundwater, aimed at identifying hydrogeodynamic effects that can serve as indicators of geodynamic processes and precursors of earthquakes. During the research, data on the hydrogeodynamic effects of earthquakes in the region were studied and dependencies between indicators of precursor of effects and parameters of seismic events were determined [11]. Short-term hydrogeological effects associated with modern movements of the earth's crust on the territory of Armenia [15] were identified. The features of hydro-

geodynamic precursor effects were studied and the information content of the observation network of Armenia was assessed [12]. The nature of hydrogeodynamic effects was revealed, preceding earthquakes in the form of changes in groundwater levels, duration and amplitude.

Results

The results of hydrogeodynamic observations for monitoring were compared with the seismic regime of the region, and a catalog of earthquakes that occurred on the territory of Armenia during study period was examined. The spatial distribution of seismic events is shown on the seismicity map of Armenia (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Map of the epicenters of earthquakes that occurred on the territory of Armenia (2018).
 - deep faults: I - Yerevan, II - Garni, III - Ararat-Sevan, IV- Bazum -Sevan, V- Pambak-Sevan-Syunik,
 VI-Axuryan, ▲ –hydrogeodynamic boreholes, o – cities; earthquake: ● - $M=2-3$, ★ - $M \geq 3$

The map reflects the distribution of earthquake epicenters ($M \geq 2$) in the region, the highest concentration of seismic events is observed in Central Armenia, mainly along the Garni fault, in the north (Javakheti highland), along the Pambak-Sevan deep fault and partly in the southwestern region [7]. The hypocenters of the occurred earthquakes are distributed at depths of up to 5-15 km, which corresponds to crustal earthquakes in Armenia. The sources of earthquakes in the

territory of Armenia have small (not exceeding 30-35 km) depths. This means that the sources of earthquakes are located in the earth's crust, which is why earthquakes are called crustal. The sources of relatively intense earthquakes are located at depths of up to 10-15 km. The developed graph of the number of earthquakes monthly for 2018 is shown in Fig. 3. High seismicity is observed in July and October of this year.

Fig.3. Distribution of occurred earthquake quantity.
 N- number of earthquakes that occurred.

Based on the parameters of hydrogeodynamic observations, a map of the hydrogeodeformation field of the earth's crust on the territory of Armenia was developed [13]. The magnitude of the calculated deformation was determined at each observation point, according to the formula: $E=(R/10^{0,413M-2,66})^{-3}$, where M is the magnitude of the earthquake, the epicentral distance – R is the distance between the observation point and the epicenter of the earthquake [1]. The studies have shown

that in the process of preparing earthquakes, effects - precursors could be recorded if the calculated deformation has a value of at least 10^{-8} , i.e. exceeds the magnitude of the earth's tidal deformation. However, as studies of precursors have shown, in some cases, with high sensitivity of the borehole-reservoir system, the preparation of earthquakes can be accompanied by effects with a larger magnitude deformation- 10^{-9} .

Fig.4. Map of stress strain state of earth's crust of Central Armenia

▲ – hydrogeodynamic borholes, – deep faults:
I - Yerevan, II - Garni, III - Ararat-Sevan, IV- Bazum -Sevan, V- Pambak-Sevan-Syunik,
VI-Akhuryan, – deformation isoline, o –cities,

Thus, a map of the hydrogeodeformation field of the earth's crust has been developed (Fig. 4), reflecting the geodynamic movements of the earth's crust in the form of local structures of deformation (compression, extension) [14]. In the northern part of the region (Gyumri and Spitak tectonic blocks) compression deformation is observed, the maximum values of the calculated deformation are numerically equal: $\varepsilon = 10^{-7}$,

10^{-6} , (Table 1) in the southeastern part of the Yerevan tectonic block (Garni fault) deformation of compression is also traced - $\varepsilon = 10^{-7}$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-8}$, tensile deformation is observed in the NE (Metsamor block), in the west (Sevan block) and in the south of the territory of Armenia [3].

Table 1

Coordinates and parametres of the occurred Earthquakes

dd.mm.yy.	Earthquake coordinates		Magnitude M	Depth H	Epicentral distance Δ, km	Observation point HGD	Estimated Deformation ε
	φ	λ					
14,01,2018	41,02	43,95	2,2	5	8,7	10	8,55E-10
14,01,2018	41,09	43,78	2,7	10	12,41	10	1,21E-08
21,01,2018	41,02	43,88	2,2	10	5,7	10	3,07E-08
24,01,2018	40,87	43,87	2	10	13,5	11	1,28E-09
24,01,2018	40,87	43,87	2,1	7	13,5	11	1,70E-09
25,02,2018	39,80	45,16	3,2	10	16,2	22	2,29E-08
25,02,2018	40,87	43,61	2,9	10	15,7	11	1,06E-08
26,03,2018	41,07	43,88	2	10	1,1	10	2,30E-06
11,04,2018	40,58	45,00	2,1	16	8,5	8	6,93E-09
06,06,2018	40,90	44,27	4,4	8	11,4	12	1,98E-06
06,06,2018	40,92	44,28	3,1	8	13,5	12	2,92E-08
06,06,2018	40,92	44,28	3,0	8	13,5	12	2,19E-08
06,06,2018	41,07	44,00	3,5	10	12,2	10	1,25E-07
06,07,2018	40,87	44,23	2,6	10	6,0	12	8,16E-08

Hydrogeodynamic data

As a result of statistical processing of the results of monitoring hydrogeodynamic observations hydrogeodynamic effects caused by the influence of the stress-

strain state of the environment was identified [4]. The work provides a graph of changes in water level in boreholes NN: 10, 10, 22 (Fig. 4 a, b, c).

Fig.5a, b, c Variations in water level in hydrogeodynamic boreholes: NN 12,10,22.

In the last diagram, the vertical lines show earthquake moments in magnitudes. The arrow indicates earthquakes.

Borehole N10 was drilled in the north of the region, where seismotectonic processes are active (Fig. 2). During the research, 10 earthquakes with $2 < M \leq 3.5$

occurred around the borehole. Before the earthquake of 06.06.2018, $M=3.5$ (Table 1), a variation in the decrease in water level in the borehole is observed (Fig. 5a), which probably indicates that near the borehole, tensile deformations prevailed, which led to a growth

in pore-fracture capacity and increase in reservoir permeability.

Borehole N12 was drilled in the zone of the active Spitak fault and within the Spitak tectonic block; the seismotectonic activity of the borehole location is determined by two factors: the geodynamics of the deep fault (movements along the fault) and the earthquakes that have occurred. The earthquake of 06.06.2018, $M=4.4$ (Table 1) occurred at an epicentral distance of 16 km from the borehole and caused a stepwise change in the water level (Fig. 5b) corresponding to compression deformation (Fig. 4).

Borehole N22 is located within a clearly defined tectonic block in Vayk. Variations in the water level in the borehole (Fig. 5c) before the earthquake of 02/25/1018, $M = 3.2$ (Table 1), characterize an increase in the level caused by a reduction in the pore crack space of the medium, occurring under the influence of compressive stresses; compression deformation was formed near the borehole (Fig. 4) [9].

Thus, based on hydrogeodynamic data, differences in the nature of deformation processes have been identified in different areas of the earth's crust in the territory of Armenia.

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Discussions

The novelty of this work lies in the assessment of the information content of each hydrogeodynamic well and the selection of a group of informative wells for recording tidal variations, changes in water level and strain sensitivity of well locations.

Analysis and processing of the results of monitoring hydrogeodynamic observations allows us to study variations in the deformation (movement) of the earth's crust in the territory of Armenia in time and space.

Widespread use and interpretation of the results obtained in the future is important for assessing the stress-strain state of the earth's crust in Armenia.

Results

The use of the hydrogeodynamic monitoring method makes it possible to assess the seismic regime of the territory of Armenia for the period under study: the number of earthquakes that occurred, the prevailing depth of the source and the magnitude of the earthquake.

The distribution of earthquake sources in time and space according to the seismicity map of the region indicates the concentration of seismic events in tectonic blocks and deep seismically active faults.

The stress-strain state of the region's crust affects the deformation of the water-bearing rocks in the well. Compressive deformation of the rock is reflected in the dynamics of the water level in the form of a rise, and tensile deformation of the rock results in a decrease in the level.

Based on the map of the stress-strain state of the earth's crust in the territory of Armenia, built according to seismicity and hydrogeodynamics indicators, it follows that the more stressed parts of the region's earth's crust for 2018 are the northern (Gyumri and Spitak tectonic blocks) and SW (Vayk block) parts of Armenia.

Spatiotemporal analysis showed patterns of development of hydrogeodeformation processes, both the distribution of geodynamic stresses and the nature of their influence on the groundwater level.

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